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Research Article

**GENDER DISPARITY IN-HOSPITAL COMPLICATIONS
AFTER PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION (PCI)
OF CULPRIT VESSEL FOR ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME
(ACS)**Dr Muhammad Hussain¹, Dr Ammar Asif², Dr Muneeb Asif³¹Punjab Institute of Cardiology Lahore, ²Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, ³Orebro University, Sweden.**Abstract**

Introduction: It has been observed that women are at more risk of Post PCI in-hospital complications i.e vascular complications, Death, Post PCI MI, Post PCI Emergency CABG/ re do PCI. This poor outcome in female as compare to male is related to number of factors including older age and higher prevalence of risk factors.
Objective: To determine the frequency of male and female undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel and gender-based comparison of in-hospital post PCI complications in these patients.

Study Design: This descriptive case series study was conducted at Coronary Care Units I, II, III Cardiology Ward, Jilani Block and Angiography Ward of Punjab Institute of Cardiology. It was non-probability purposive sampling. A total of 135 PCI of culprit vessels were done from 19 December 2012 to 18 May. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications.

Results: Out of total 135 patients undergoing Culprit vessel PCI male 75 (55.55%) were more as compare to female 60(44.44%). Post PCI Complications were significantly higher in females as compare to males. i.e hematoma 35(31.81%) in female as compare to 10(9.09%) in males. MI female 15(13.63%) males 5(4.54%), Death females 2 (3.6%) males 1(1.8%) and CABG 0 (0%) in both males and females.

Conclusion: This study shows that in Pakistan PCI of Culprit vessel is more in males as compare to females and females are at increased risk of post PCI complications i.e Vascular complications and Post PCI MI and death but emergency CABG after PCI is the same in both genders.

Key Words: Percutaneous Intervention, Culprit Vessel, Gender disparity, Vascular Complications.

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INTRODUCTION:

Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) is the most common interventional procedure used for Coronary revascularization. The number of PCI is increasing with the passage of time due to increased awareness and improved outcomes compared to fibrinolytic therapy for coronary artery disease (CAD) [1]. Meta-analyses of randomized clinical trials have reported that primary PCI is more cost effective compared to fibrinolytic and reduces the incidence of death, reinfarction and stroke. Furthermore in stable patients and in patients with multivessel disease, PCI has become the preferred procedure in the united states with declining mortality in patients undergoing multivessel PCI [2].

PCI also has got many complications like other interventions i.e Death, myocardial infarction (MI), emergency CABG or re do PCI, stroke, contrast induced nephropathy (CIN) Vascular complications before intervention [3]. GpIIb/IIIa inhibitors have reduced the mortality by 20% over 6-12 months in unstable angina and non ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI). PCI has not shown any mortality benefit in stable angina. Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in women. Sex based differences has been area of active investigation over the past two decades [4]. Symptoms of females appear at elder age as compare to male, however the symptoms of females are atypical as compare to males. The diagnosis is more difficult in females and prognosis is less favorable [5]. It has reported in several studies that female undergo intervention less frequently as compare to males. PCI on females is usually is usually more complicated due to gender related small sized coronary arteries [6]. Thus females are at more risk of post PCI complications and also at increased risk of mortality and morbidity [7].

OBJECTIVE:

1. To determine the frequency of male and female undergoing PCI of culprit vessel.
2. To compare in-hospital post PCI complications of culprit vessel between male and female.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive case series study was conducted at Coronary Care Units I, II, III Cardiology Ward, Jilani Block and Angiography Ward of Punjab Institute of Cardiology. It was non-probability purposive sampling. A total of 135 PCI of culprit vessels were done from 19 December 2012 to 18 May. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and

females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. PCI in patients who are admitted with ACS.
2. PCI in both males and females' patients >30 years of age
3. PCI with either bare metal stents (BMS) or drug eluting stents (DES)
4. PCI for single vessel disease (SVD) i.e culprit vessel.
5. PCI through radial or femoral route.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Previous PCI or CABG
2. Left main Stem (LMS) PCI
3. Plain and balloon angioplasty (POBA)

DATA COLLECTION:

A total of 135 PCI of culprit vessels were done from 19 December 2012 to 18 May 2013 in Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore. These patients were admitted to hospital with ACS. These patients received Primary, Rescue and facilitated PCI. 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) out of these 135 patients were selected. Written consent was taken before starting the study protocol. Detail History with demographic features was taken and patients were divided in two groups on the basis of gender. Risk factors were also stratified i.e

- Diabetes Mellitus (fasting blood sugar >126 mg/dl and Random >200 mg/dl)
- Hypertension (sustained elevation in blood pressure of >140/80 or previous history) and smoking.

DATA ANALYSIS:

All data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS (statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 12 for window. Continuous (Age, BMI) and Categorical variables (Gender, procedural complications i.e CIN, Hematoma, MI. etc), were presented as mean± standard deviation and frequency/percentages respectively. Risk factors for IHD i.e diabetes mellitus and hypertension, smoking and hyperlipidemia are presented as frequency tables.

RESULTS:

A total of 135 angioplasties of culprit vessel were done from December 18 2012 to May 17 2013. These patients were admitted in Punjab institute of cardiology with ACS. Males were more in number as compared to females. i.e 75 males (55.55%) and 60 females (44.44%). Out of these 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) were selected for this study. These patients were fulfilling the Inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline characteristics of the patients who underwent PCI are shown below in

table 1. Mean age of the male patients was 49.8 ± 9.60 while that of female patients was 52.1 ± 8.91 .

Out of 525 male patients who underwent PCI, 21% of the patients were diabetics. Hypertension was present in 46% of the male patients. Among the female patients the incidence of diabetes and hypertension was 29% and 53% respectively. The mean body mass index (BMI) of female patients was also higher than the male patients i.e 30.2 vs 28.6 respectively.

TABLE 1. Base line characteristics

Variable	Male	Female
Age, years	49.8 ± 9.60	52.1 ± 8.91
Diabetes Mellitus	25.45%(14)	32.72%(18)
Hypertension	50.90%(28)	56.36%(31)

TABLE 2. This table below shows the comparison of indications for percutaneous Intervention between males and females.**TABLE 2. Indications for PCI**

	Male(55)	Female(55)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (primary)	14.54%(8)	5.45%(3)
Acute Myocardial Infarction(rescue)	5.45%(3)	3.63%(2)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (elective)	41.81%(23)	56.36(31)
NSTEMI	27.27%(15)	25.45%(14)
Unstable Angina	10.90%(6)	9.09%(5)

Characteristics of the procedure are shown here

TABLE 3. Procedural Characteristics

	Male	Female
Radial PCI	96.36% (53)	94.54%(52)
Femoral PCI	3.6% (2)	5.45 % (3)
GPIIb/IIIa Inhibitor used	85.45%(47)	74.54%(41)
Bare Metal Stent (BMS)	21.81%(12)	29.09%(16)
Drug Eluted Stent(DES)	78.18%(43)	70.90%(39)

The table given below shows the difference in in-hospital complications between males and females.

Cumulative vascular complications were significantly higher in female population as compared to males while there was no significant difference of contrast

induced nephropathy between both the groups.

DISCUSSION:

Main function of heart is to provide circulatory needs of the body. Heart also need its own metabolic requirements. These requirements are met through the coronary blood flow. Heart needs aerobic metabolism, there is limited capacity of heart to tolerate anaerobic metabolism. Heart has a unique mechanism of oxygen extraction. Under basal condition it extract high degree of oxygen so that it can adjust a changing oxygen needs by only a small increment in oxygen extraction [8]. There is more coronary blood flow if there's more need of oxygen to the cardiac muscle. To measure the oxygen consumption by cardiac muscle certain studies have been done on animals [9]. It is very difficult to calculate the mean myocardial oxygen consumptions (MVO₂) there is laboratory data that can be used to measure MVO₂. To meet the bad time heart has sufficient reservoir of oxygen [10].

Oxygen consumption correlated with the tension time index only until the peak systolic pressure had been attained at which 91% of oxygen consumption per beat had occurred. Oxygen consumption is not uniform throughout the systole (tension time index). It is due to the insensitivity to the duration of pressure maintenance between peak systolic pressure and the end of relaxation. Wall stress is more related to MVO₂ [11].

It is calculated that about 20% of the oxygen consumption of the working heart is the basal oxygen requirement of the potassium plegic heart [12-13]. It has also been determined that oxygen requirement of electrical activation of the heart has been determined to be less than 1% of the oxygen need of the normal working [14].

CONCLUSION:

It is the total obstruction of the artery usually at the site of access requiring surgical repair. Conclusion is defined as total obstruction of blood vessel usually due to the thrombus formation dissection or other mechanisms usually at the site of access of plaque pulse or Doppler signal and associated with sign and symptoms of an ischemic limb requiring surgical intervention.

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